

**OSHQOZON YARA KASALIKLARI VA ULARNING KELIB CHIQISH
SABABLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda oshqozon yara kasalliklari va ularning kelib chiqish sababi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Unda oshqozon yara kasalliklari yara turlarini ajratish, yara kasallik bosqichlarini tasniflash, kasallikning klinik, anatomik kechish jarayoni borasida fikrlar yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Xlorid kislota, yara(yazva), ovqatlanish tartibi, mahsulot, parhez.

Abstract: This thesis presents information about stomach ulcer diseases and their causes. It contains thoughts on the classification of ulcer types, classification of ulcer disease stages, and the clinical and anatomical course of the disease.

Key words: Hydrochloric acid, ulcer, diet, product, diet

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о язвенных заболеваниях желудка и их причинах. Содержит мысли о классификации типов язв, классификации стадий язвенной болезни, клинико-анатомическом течении заболевания.

Ключевые слова: Соляная кислота, язва, диета, продукт, диета.

Muammoning dolzarbligi: O'z vaqtida ovqatlanmaslik sababli odamlarda ko'pgina oshqozon yaralari kelib chiqishi. Oshqozon yarasi odamning ovqatlanish tartibiga rioya qilmaslik, o'z vaqtida ovqatlanmasligi va ko'pgina kimyoviy moddalar qo'shilgan mahsulotlarni iste'mol qilishi orqali kelib chiqadi. O'z vaqtida ovqatlanmaslik sababli oshqozon tarkibidagi xlorid kislotani ishlab chiqarilishi sababli oshqozon shilliq pardasini yemirishi kuzatiladi. Oshqozon shilliq qavati yemirilgandan so'ng oshqozon kislata tushgan joylarda yazva hosil bo'ladi va o'sha yaradan qon ketishi mumkin bu holatlar ko'pincha abituryent va talabalarda kuzatiladi. Oshqozon yara kasalliklarini kelib chiqishiga sabab bo'luvchi oziq mahsulotlar: gazli ichimliklar va fast food mahsulotlari kiradi.

Tadqiqot ishning maqsadi oshqozon yara kasaligini kelib chiqish sababini o'rganishdan iborat.

Tadqiqot davomida quyidagi vazifalar belgilab olindi.

- ❖ Oshqozon yara turlarini ajratish;
- ❖ Oshqozon yara kasallik bosqichlarini tasniflash.

Tadqiqot natijasi:

1. Oshqozon yara turiga qarab:

- A) yakka
- B) ko'pchilik

2. Yara diametriga qarab:

- A) kichkina diametrli 0,5 sm gacha
- B) o'rta diametrli 0,5-1sm gacha
- C) katta diametrli 1,1-2,9sm

D) ulkan (juda katta), me'da yarasi uchun 3sm va ortiq, o'n ikki barmoqli ichak yarasi uchun 2sm dan ortiq

3. Klinik kechishiga qarab:

- A) tipik
- B) notipik - notipik og'riq sindromi bilan - og'riqsiz (lekin boshqa klinik belgilar bilan) – simptomsiz turlarga ajratildi.

4. Oshqozon yara kasallik bosqichiga qarab

- A) zo'rayishi
- B) remissiya (kasallikning yengillashishi)
- klinik - anatomik: a) epitelizatsiyalash b) chandiqlanish (qizil va oq chandiqlanish) C) funksional

5. Asoratlar mavjudligiga qarab

- A) Qon ketishi
- B) Penetratsiya
- C) Teshilish
- D) Stenozlanish
- E) Malignizatsiya holatlari bilan tasniflandi.

Xulosa: Oshqozonda yazva hosil bo'lganda qat'iy parhez tutish shart bunda bemorning ahvoriga qarab 14 kundan - 1 yoki 2 oygacha parhez tutish tavsiya etiladi bunda: nordon, achiq, qatiq, juda sovuq va issiq, qovurilgan oziq ovqatlar taqiqlanadi.

O'z vaqtida ovqatlanish tartibiga rioya qilmaslik va fast food, gazlangan ichimliklar tufayli kelib chiqishi mumkin ekan demak bu kasallik bilan kasallanmaslik uchun o'z vaqtida ovqatlanib turli xil kimyoviy moddalar qo'shilgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarni iste'mol qilishni cheklash zarur.

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